

Effects of Dynamic Irradiation on Light-Driven Catalyzed Water Oxidation (Supporting Information)

Alina Koba^{a,†}, Daniel Kowalczyk^{a,†}, Lena Kunik^a, Kevin Siewerth^b, Akuila Edwards^c, Silvia Katolla^d,
Boris Mizaikoff^d, Michael Schmitt^c, Jürgen Popp^{c,e}, Sven Rau^b, Dirk Ziegenbalg^{a,*}

^aInstitute of Chemical Engineering, Ulm University, Albert-Einstein-Allee 11, 89081 Ulm, Germany.

^bInstitute of Inorganic Chemistry I, Ulm University, Albert-Einstein-Allee 11, 89081 Ulm, Germany.

^cInstitute of Physical Chemistry, Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Helmholtzweg 4, 07743 Jena, Germany.

^dInstitute of Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry, Ulm University, Albert-Einstein-Allee 11, 89081 Ulm, Germany.

^eLeibnitz Institute for Photonic Technologies, e.V. Jena, Albert-Einstein-Straße 9, 07745 Jena, Germany.

[†]These authors contributed equally.

* dirk.ziegenbalg@uni-ulm.de

Table of Contents

Effects of Dynamic Irradiation on Light-Driven Ru(bpy) Catalyzed Water Oxidation	1
Materials and Methods	3
Detailed Information on Reagents and Instruments	3
Gravimetric Volume Determination	3
Detailed Information on Experimental Setups	3
Twin Setup	3
NGA Setup	3
Bypass Setup	3
Radiometric LED characterization	3
Multi-spectroscopy Setup	5
Raman and ATR-IR Measurement Cell	5
Detailed Information on Software e.g. Python Scripts	5
Experimental Details – DATEN MÜSSEN NOCH BESCHRIFTET WERDEN	6
Raman Results – Static (S2O82- @ 1074 cm-1, SO42- @ 978 cm-1)	6
Raman Results – Pulsed (S2O82- @ 1074 cm-1, SO42- @ 978 cm-1)	7
ATR-IR – Static (S2O82- @ 1276 cm-1, SO42- @ 1100 cm-1)	8
ATR-IR – Pulsed (S2O82- @ 1276 cm-1, SO42- @ 1100 cm-1)	9
FireSting	10
UV/Vis	11
UV/Vis - Static	12
UV/Vis – Pulsed	13
Twin Setup – Vial Photos	15

Materials and Methods

Detailed Information on Reagents and Instruments

Gravimetric Volume Determination

For “8 mL” GC vials (used in twin and NGA setups) and Schlenk vial (used in bypass setup)

Detailed Information on Experimental Setups

Twin Setup

Single 8 mL (8.3 mL) GC vial in modular photoreactor (ref: DK) modified with additional openings for FireSting optical fibers (2x temperature, 2x oxygen).

NGA Setup

Single 8 mL (8.3 mL) GC vial in modular photoreactor (ref: DK) modified to fit NGA vial holder.

Bypass Setup

Schlenk vial used as reactor vessel, equipped with Schlenk hose adapter for nitrogen flushing and four GL14 threads for two BOLA HT laboratory screw joint connectors to connect to Cole-Parmer 1/8” OD 1/16” ID PVDF capillaries, other two threads covered by BOLA HT screw caps.

Modified modular photoreactor to fit large Schlenk vial and openings at the top to pass through capillaries.

Capillaries connected to Schlenk vial via BOLA HT laboratory screw joint connectors, connected to KNF SIMDOS®10 FEM 1.10 TT.18 RC-P diaphragm liquid dosing pump and Raman + ATR-IR measurement cell via Idex PEEK flangeless ¼-28 UNF flat bottom fittings.

Radiometric LED characterization

Integrating sphere MSP UK150P-REFLTRANS, Mountain Photonics (10 mm port) for spectral and integral radiation power measurement, connected to AvaSpec-ULS2048CL-EVO-RS-UA via fiber optic cable FC-UVIR600-2-ME-SMA

EQ99X LDLS, ENERGETIQ light source as reference, calibrated to a standard lamp (BN-LHSF-AP-100, Gigahertz Optik) according to ISO17025

Multidimensional spectroscopy: reference Sender publications

Table 1: Measured LED radiant power of pulsed and static setup. [*] denotes interpolated values based on values measured with an integrating sphere radiometry setup.

I / mA	$\Phi_{e,\text{pulsed}}$ / mW	$q_{P,\text{pulsed}}$ / $\mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$	$\Phi_{e,\text{static}}$ / mW	$q_{P,\text{static}}$ / $\mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$
100	100.0	0.471	95.6	0.446
350	303.8*	1.190*	289.5*	1.128*
400	369.1	1.333	344.0	1.264
500	413.9*	1.621*	392.8*	1.536*
700	564.5	2.196	555.6	2.081
1000	768.5	3.058	714.0	2.899

Multi-spectroscopy Setup

Raman and ATR-IR Measurement Cell

Detailed Information on Software e.g. Python Scripts

Evaluation equations for TON, TOF, photonic efficiency, rel. TON and rel. photonic efficiency

Experimental Details – DATEN MÜSSEN NOCH BESCHRIFTET WERDEN

Raman Results – Static ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ @ 1074 cm^{-1} , SO_4^{2-} @ 978 cm^{-1})

Raman Results – Pulsed ($S_2O_8^{2-}$ @ 1074 cm^{-1} , SO_4^{2-} @ 978 cm^{-1})

ATR-IR – Static (S₂O₈²⁻ @ 1276 cm⁻¹, SO₄²⁻ @ 1100 cm⁻¹)

ATR-IR – Pulsed ($S_2O_8^{2-}$ @ 1276 cm^{-1} , SO_4^{2-} @ 1100 cm^{-1})

FireSting

UV/Vis

UV/Vis - Static

UV/Vis – Pulsed

Figure 1: Relative turn over number and relative photonic efficiency as functions of duty cycle, pulse frequency and pulse duration. Experiments performed at $I = 350\text{-}1000 \text{ mA}$, $f = 2\text{-}1000 \text{ Hz}$, $\text{DC} = 5\text{-}45\%$. The horizontal plane in the diagrams showing the relative photonic efficiency indicates a value of 1.

Twin Setup – Vial Photos

Figure 2: Twin setup vials right after experiment (left) and after cleaning (right), with the right vial (pulsed setup) showing a change in reaction solution color and black discoloration on and around oxygen sensor spots in liquid phase.